

Avian spring migration at the east Adriatic coast: coastal and sea-crossing dynamics of intensity, timing, and flight directions

Simon Hirschhofer ²

¹ Department of Geography, University of Zurich, Zürich, Switzerland

² Department of Bird Migration, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland

Correspondence: Simon Hirschhofer (simon.hirschhofer@geo.uzh.ch)

Abstract. Simultaneous nocturnal bird migration across and along geographical barriers can lead to very complex spatiotemporal patterns of directions and intensity. Understanding these is necessary to coordinate dynamic conservation actions such as the temporal shut down of disturbing illumination or potentially harmful wind turbines. Previously, it was suggested that within-night timing of migrants is partially related to upstream geographical features. We used radar monitoring to record two years of spring migration to investigate these dynamics at the coast of Croatia. With FPCA and hierarchical clustering, we tried to disentangle the relationship between within-night timing of migration and related flight directions. However, our analysis has demonstrated that although distinct patterns have been observed over the season, within-night timing was not necessarily connected to a distinct preferred migration direction.

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Background

Each spring, vast numbers of migratory birds migrate through the east Adriatic coastal region, following different routes to reach their breeding grounds in central or northern Europe. Some birds migrate along the coast

on a southeast to northwest axis, while others cross the Adriatic Sea between Italy and Croatia on a southwest to northeast axis (Kiepenheuer and Linsenmair, 1965; Kralj et al., 2013). Understanding the interplay between these two migratory streams is critical to improving our knowledge of key migratory corridors and informing conservation efforts (Hirschhofer et al., 2023). While past research in the area has primarily relied on bird ringing and observational studies (Kralj and Dolenc, 2008; Radović et al., 1999; Stipčević, 1997), quantitative data of high temporal resolution were lacking. Moreover, as most birds migrate at night, visual methods are often limited. This study employs bird radar to quantitatively analyse migration patterns in real time, setting a particular focus on migration intensity and flight directions within single nights.

Methods

We deployed four mobile radar stations along the Croatian coast (Figure 1), two in Istria (at the Palud ornithological reserve and in Rovinj, 6.7 km apart) and two in Dalmatia (at Lake Vrana and in Zadar, 30.4 km apart).

The radars continuously recorded avian activity during the spring migration seasons of 2023 and 2024, from March to May. We extracted only nocturnal data, resulting in an initial dataset of 728 nights for the four sites, of which we excluded 148 nights due to technical problems and rain contamination. The radars measured, among other things, the birds' precise flight direction, altitude, ground speed and wing flapping. The detection of wing flapping allowed a rough classification into

taxonomic groups and thus a focus of the study on passerine migrants. This conservative approach minimised the risk of false positives due to the very distinctive flapping pattern of passerines.

The primary objective was to determine how migration intensities and flight directions varied between the two regions and whether the timing of peak migration intensity within a given night could be linked to sea-crossing or coastal migration. It was expected that coastal migration would dominate the early part of the night, with birds flying northwest along the coast, while sea-crossing migration to the northeast would be more pronounced later in the night, due to the time delay caused by crossing the 130-200 km wide geographical barrier of the Adriatic Sea.

Figure 1 Map overview of the study region, showing the two expected migratory streams across the Adriatic Sea (blue) and along the Croatian coast (red).

We worked with individual bird echoes to analyse flight directions. To quantify migratory flows, we used a standard method in radar ornithology, where echoes are aggregated on an hourly time resolution, considering the altitude-dependent detection probability bias due to the shape of the radar beam and the size of a bird (Schmid et al., 2019).

Results and discussion

The results reveal strong temporal and spatial variations in migration intensity and flight directions that are not necessarily linked to each other. In March, recorded bird activity was highly synchronised across all sites, suggesting relatively homogeneous broad front migration. However, by April, differences between sites became more pronounced, and by May, migration intensity had become highly variable, especially between Istria and Dalmatia. The highest levels of migration activity were recorded in March and in May, while in April, the migration intensity was relatively low across all sites (Figure 2, Figure 3). This pattern aligns with previous

research indicating that short-distance migrants dominate early-season movements, while long-distance migrants from sub-Saharan Africa increase in numbers later in spring (Gargallo et al., 2011).

Flight direction analysis provided further insight into the dynamics of coastal vs. sea-crossing migration. In March, birds primarily migrated in a north-northeast direction throughout the night, suggesting that a significant proportion were arriving from across the Adriatic Sea. In April, directional patterns began to diverge. While early-night migration was dominated by northwest and even westward flying birds, indicating strong coastal migration or movement towards offshore islands, migration directions later in the night shifted towards the north or north-northeast, reflecting the arrival of sea-crossing migrants. By May, this trend was even more pronounced, with a clear division between early-night coastal and late-night sea-crossing migration.

To explore whether within-night timing could be used to distinguish coastal from sea-crossing migration, we applied functional principal component analysis (FPCA) and hierarchical clustering of eigenvalues to classify different avian activity profiles based on within night migration intensity. While most nights were characterised by low-intensity migration, other nights featured intense migratory activity with either early or late peaks. Importantly, nights with early peaks in migration intensity were often associated with coastal migration, while nights with delayed peaks showed stronger signs of sea-crossing migration (Figure 4). However, contrary to initial hypotheses, these patterns were not entirely consistent across the study sites, suggesting that additional factors such as wind influenced the timing of migratory activity.

Figure 2 Nocturnal migration intensity across the Adriatic Sea in 2023

Figure 3 Nocturnal migration intensity along the Croatian coast in 2023.

Figure 4 Comparison of flight directions in Dalmatia for nights with early and late intensity peaks. The colours refer to four quarters of the night: after sunset (blue), before midnight (purple), after midnight (orange), and before sunrise (yellow).

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the complexity of bird migration along the east Adriatic coast in particular, and in the presence of topographic obstacles in general. Rather than a simple division between coastal and sea-crossing migration, the results indicate a fluid interaction between the two, shaped by seasonality, weather conditions and likely other environmental predictors. Most importantly, migration intensity and directionality vary not only between nights, but also within them. While birds moving along the barrier appear early after sunset, barrier-crossing birds arrive later, with their timing being likely more dependent on environmental conditions. However, because we did not completely succeed in modelling migratory direction from the variability in peak timing alone, further research should integrate meteorological data and tracking technologies to refine our understanding of the factors influencing migratory routes and corresponding arrival times.

From a conservation perspective, these results underscore the need for dynamic protective measures tailored to migration timing and intensity. Late-arriving migrants that crossed the sea might be especially vulnerable to

offshore wind farms and light pollution on land. Short-term interventions, such as reducing artificial lighting or temporarily shutting down wind turbines during peak migration could help mitigate risks to migratory birds. Being able to predict coastal and sea-crossing migration intensity in real-time could significantly increase the efficiency of conservation measurements and reduce their costs due to better temporal limitations, ensuring safer passage for birds along one of Europe's key migratory corridors.

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Competing interests. The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Data availability. All data can be provided on request.

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